

New public discoveries in 2022 against a backdrop of concerns about reporting and processing of finds

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INTRODUCTION

This article summarises recent public finds from Estonia and gives a brief overview of recent developments in their management by the National Heritage Board (hereafter MA). Most of the discoveries discussed were made by licensed hobbyists using metal detectors and only a few by chance (e.g. nos 44, 142, 146). The recreational use of search devices, primarily metal detectors, remains popular, with the number of licence holders reaching almost 1,000 individuals in 2022 (949 licence holders), representing an increase of 87 individuals compared to the previous year. The volume of reported finds, however, has not increased at the same rate. Looking at the 2022 data, there are more than a hundred records less compared to the 274 entries mentioned in the 2021 article (Kurisoo *et al.* 2022, table 1). The possible reasons for this worrying development are discussed in the second half of this paper.

Information on new discoveries is presented in Table 1, which encompasses all discoveries reported to the MA in 2022, regardless of the actual discovery date. As in previous years, certain deliberate exclusions have been made to enhance data clarity. For example, unidentifiable artefacts and single finds representing modern mass material have been excluded from the dataset. Finds from different search activities, but from the same find spot, have been grouped together. Most of the determinations (site types, artefact types and dates) are provisional and subject to change over time.

RESULTS

Northern parts of Estonia: Harju, Ida-Viru, Järva, Lääne-Viru, and Rapla Counties

Compared to previous years, the number of finds reported from the northern parts of Estonia has decreased significantly (Fig. 1; Table 1). This decline is particularly noticeable in Harju County (26 find spots) and Ida-Viru County (only 10 find spots), which have been among

Fig. 1. Public finds that reached the MA in 2022.

Jn 1. 2022. aastal MA-sse jõudnud juhuleiud ja hobitsijate leiud.

Map / Kaart: Estonian Land Board / Maa amet (administrative and settlement units / haldusjaotus); Sander Jegerov

the main areas of interest for hobbyists since the use of metal detectors was regulated in 2011 (e.g. Ots & Rammo 2013, 301). The search activity in Lääne-Viru (28 find spots), Järva (20 find spots) and Rapla (5 find spots) Counties correlates more with the trends of the recent years (e.g. Kurisoo *et al.* 2021; 2022). At the same time, the northern parts of the country are still areas with the highest number of search activities. More than half of the find spots can be contextualized, among those settlement sites (37 find spots) and burial places dominate (26 find spots). Additionally, three hoards and a smithy were discovered.

The oldest artefacts, two pieces of worked flint, were found in Viskla (no. 26), and they originate from the Stone Age (9000–1750 BC). The dataset also includes a Late Bronze Age socketed axe (no. 22) and a single Roman Iron Age find, an eye fibula (no. 2). As expected, the majority of the metal detector finds can be dated to the end of the prehistoric period, and in particular to the 11th to 13th centuries, which corresponds to the Final Iron Age. The finds are mainly local ornaments and dress accessories, including brooches, bracelets, belt details and other related items. The majority of such finds come from burial sites with cremations (e.g. nos 2, 11, 56, 63, 71, 81, 87, 101, 129, 130), while a smaller number can be associated with settlement sites (e.g. nos 2, 9, 61, 64, 89, 92) or are currently considered to be stray finds (e.g. nos 3, 4, 34, 74, 97). The only Viking Age hoard from the northern parts of Estonia was found in the village of Aa (no. 30), consisting of two cross-headed dress pins and fragments of a spiral bracelet. The Aa find assemblage was unearthed from a former wetland, which may suggest ritual significance.

There are three artefacts from the Final Iron Age that deserve highlighting. The first is a sword scabbard chape found in Saue (no. 19), distinguished by its unique anthropomorphic motif, which lacks known parallels in the region (Fig. 2: 1). Most of the Late Iron Age sword scabbard chapes feature geometric motifs and rarely zoomorphic motifs (Jets 2013, 148; Selirand 1974, 120). Moreover, anthropomorphic depictions are uncommon in the local archaeological record and are usually associated with pieces of jewellery (see more in Kurisoo 2021, 269–270). The overall shape and design of the Saue example bear resemblance to scabbard chapes belonging to Tomsons' type IIIa-1, dating from the 11th century to the first half of the 12th century (Tomsons 2019, 147–149). Another rare artefact is an ear scoop from the village of Vilivalla (no. 25; Fig. 2: 2). Although there are other hygienic or cosmetic objects from the end of the prehistoric period, namely small bone spades (see more in Luik & Tamla 2006), there are notably fewer items made of copper alloys. The ear scoop from Vilivalla is similar to Finnish finds, which Ella Kivikoski (1973, 1215) has dated to 1050–1150 on the basis of the Mikkeli-Tuukkala burial. The third case is a pendant from Ärina (no. 105; Fig 2: 3). So far, two nearly identical pendants depicting a rider on a horse have been documented in Estonia: one from Ranna and the other from Marinu (Kurisoo 2021, fig. 3.42; 109). The recent discovery from Ärina is a third example, and all these pendants were found in Lääne-Viru County. What distinguishes these finds, particularly, is their technical execution. The Ranna pendant (AI 2510: 2) is well-crafted and may have served as a model for the Marinu example (AI 7148: 1). In contrast, the Ärina pendant exhibits a coarser craftsmanship and a lower level of artistry. The craftsman of the Ärina pendant encountered difficulties in depicting the horse; it lacks a distinct and slender silhouette, while the depiction of the rider aligns more closely with the original intention.

Artefacts from the Middle Ages (1200/1250–1558 AD) and from the Modern Period (1558 AD onwards) are also well represented. Several of the settlement sites have also yielded medieval and Modern Period finds (e.g. nos 9, 10, 21, 63, 67, 94, 100) among which dress accessories, ornaments and small everyday objects dominate. Medieval and Modern Period stray finds are similarly representative of common material from the period, mostly bracelets, brooches,

Fig. 2. Rare Final Iron Age items. 1 – Saue sword scabbard chape, 2 – Vilivalla ear scoop, 3 – Ärina pendant.

Jn 2. Haruldased hilisrauaaegsed esemed. 1 – mõõgatupe otsik Sauelt, 2 – Vilivalla kõrvalusikas, 3 – Ärina ripats.

Photo / Foto: Tuuli Kurisoo

dress-pins, mounts, pendants, rings, etc. (e.g. nos 16, 29, 38, 84, 103, 131). A smithy dated to the Modern Period was discovered in Meremõisa (no. 8) as suggested by the smithy tools and slag (Jegorov 2022). Lastly, two Early Modern Period hoards should also be mentioned. The one more modest in terms of composition was found in the Saka (no. 35) village in Ida-Viru County. The hoard consisted of two pewter jugs of which one had largely decayed, contained ten mostly round sheet pendants made of poor quality silver (Russow 2022a). A more impressive set of jewellery was found from Metsla-Ellavere (no. 65) in Järva County. The contents of the Metsla-Ellavere hoard include various silver ornaments (e.g. large beads, various pendants, finger-rings), numerous glass beads and looped coins, which were buried in a metal vessel in the early 17th century (Russow 2023a).

Western parts of Estonia: Hiiu, Lääne, Pärnu, and Saare Counties

As in previous years, information regarding the western parts of Estonia remains limited when compared to the northern and southern areas (see Fig. 1; Table 1). The only notable exception is Pärnu County, which is the only county in the whole dataset to show some growth in reported finds (19 find spots in total). This development can be attributed to a few hobby searchers who have focused more on the region in question. For the second consecutive year, finds with cultural value were also recovered from the island of Hiiumaa (2 find spots). Only three find spots from Lääne County can be listed in Table 1. The situation is also worrying in Saaremaa, where only eight find spots are recorded, marking a significant decrease compared to previous years (cf. Kurisoo *et al.* 2020; 2021; 2022). Moreover, Saaremaa is one of the regions known for the active use of metal detectors, but many finds are discovered illegally and do not reach the state and researchers (see also below).

In terms of find contexts information about the western parts of Estonia is similar to the northern parts. Settlements (13 find spots) and burials (7 find spots) are more numerous than other site types. Hoards were discovered only in Pärnu County, with two of them found in Metsaküla village (see below). Additionally, it is probable that the Roman denarii found in Võitra village (no. 126) constitute the third hoard found from the western part of Estonia. The Roman silver denarii are rare coins in Estonia and Võitra specimens are an important addition, although the circumstances of the discovery are somewhat ambivalent and difficult to interpret (Koovit & Kiudsoo 2023, 46).

Only a few finds from western Estonia date from an earlier period than the Late Iron Age. The oldest artefact discovered is a socketed bronze axe (1300–900 BC; Paavel 2023a) from the village of Kassari (no. 27) that used to be a separate island next to Hiiumaa, which is followed by the already mentioned denarii from Võitra. Diverse small finds dominate among the remaining material and most of the finds belong to widespread types common in the Late Iron Age (e.g. nos 75, 109, 111, 120, 136) or Modern Period (e.g. nos 76, 135, 137, 139).

The most remarkable stray find from the western parts of Estonia was discovered on the island of Saaremaa. The Länga (no. 133) waist chain is exceptional for several reasons. Such ornaments are believed to have been common ornaments for women (and children) on Saaremaa (Kustin 1962, 342–343). Most of the finds are fragments and only six partial chains are known from inhumation burials (Rannaäär 2022a, 12–13). The Länga specimen is the first find that is preserved intact and confirms that such items were probably wrapped around the waist. The Länga chain is made of rectangular chain links, rings, and spirals and is almost 2.5 metres long (Rannaäär 2022b). The chain has an oval buckle at one end and a cross-shaped pendant on the other; twelve small rumbler bells were attached to the ornament by

small chains (Fig. 3). Such waist chains (and the individual rectangular links) are usually dated to the 12th–13th centuries (e.g. Kustin 1962, 343), but the cross-shaped pendant (Valk 2001, plate XXI: 7) and the rumbler bells (Ligi 1993, plate 17: 1–3; Valk 2001, plate XX: 12) suggest a somewhat later date for the Länga specimen. Unfortunately, the circumstances surrounding the discovery are controversial. The person who found the item was involved in unauthorised and illegal search activities and chose not to report the discovery. The waist chain was subsequently reburied and, after some time, the finder finally informed the MA about the discovery, led archaeologists to the find and showed them the original location of the find.

Among the sites of the western parts of Estonia, Metsaküla that is located ca. 20 km south of Pärnu, stands out. In addition to a single spearhead (no. 119), there is evidence of two settlement sites (nos 118, 120), but more interestingly, two hoards have also been discovered. One of them is a coin hoard (no. 116) with a medieval date. The second hoard (no. 117), buried around the early 1700s, is more unique in its composition. The finds were concealed in a pewter bottle with a screw-cap (Fig. 4), which contained three silver brooches of different types (a heart-shaped brooch, an engagement brooch, and a small round brooch), one finger-ring with a depiction of hands, and a coin pendant made of 2 mark of Charles XI of Sweden, struck in 1665. Curiously, the bottle also included pieces of wax, of which purpose is currently unknown (Russow 2023b).

Fig. 3. Länga waist chain.
Jn 3. Länga vöökett.
 (SM 10954: 1.)
 Photo / Foto: Jaana Ratas

Fig. 4. *The pewter bottle of the Metsaküla hoard.*

Jn 4. *Metsaküla aarde tinapudel.*

Photo / Foto: Jaana Ratas

Southern parts of Estonia: Jõgeva, Põlva, Tartu, Valga, Viljandi and Võru Counties

The decrease in the number of records in Table 1 is also noticeable in the southern parts of Estonia, although the decrease per county is smaller than in the northern and western parts. When compared to recent years, similar levels of information are available for the counties of Jõgeva (16 find spots), Põlva (2 find spots), Võru (3 find spots), and Viljandi (7 find spots). In Tartu County, the amount of information has gradually decreased in recent years, resulting in the total of 9 find spots this time. Valga County has only two entries in Table 1. It can be concluded that the use of search devices continues to be more popular in Tartu and Jõgeva Counties and information from the rest of southern Estonia remains scarce or underreported. Stray finds dominate (e.g. nos 43, 53, 106, 141, 146, 153, 160), but information about

settlement sites (e.g. nos 40, 51, 140, 158) and burials (e.g. nos 49, 107, 149, 155) is represented in Table 1. Additionally, three hoards (nos 41, 144, 145) and a scrap metal deposit (no. 48) were unearthed in the southern parts of Estonia.

While the number of reported sites has decreased, the number of interesting discoveries has fortunately not. The MA received two Stone Age, one Bronze Age and several Roman Iron Age artefacts from the southern parts of Estonia. Both Stone Age finds were discovered without the use of metal detectors. The Kavastu adze (no. 142) was retrieved from the River Emajõgi during a fishing trip when the discoverer spotted an intriguing item on the riverbed. The Kavastu adze is certainly an important find, which could also be an indication of a new Neolithic settlement site (Kristiina Johanson (TÜ), pers. comm). The second Stone Age find, a spearhead made of flint, was found on the beach of Mustvee (no. 44) in 2009. This is a Late Neolithic (2800 BC–1750 BC) find, the only tanged spearhead of its type and material known from Estonia. Moreover, compared to arrowheads, flint spearheads are relatively scarce in the Estonian archaeological record, which makes this discovery even more noteworthy (Roio 2022). The year 2022 brought an addition to the palstaves, with the addition of a find from Vadi (no. 53). The Estonian palstaves are dated to the period of 1500–1300 BC and the total number of such finds is less than 20, with the main distribution areas being south-western and central Estonia (Paavel 2023b). The Vadi specimen from Jõgeva County is therefore an important addition to the current knowledge. A number of sites yielded single Roman Iron Age artefacts, which included crossbar fibulae from Selli (no. 49) and Sassi (no. 147), a head shield fibula from Tiidu (no. 150) and single Roman coins from Hurmi (no. 106) and Hilläkeste (no. 158).

The majority of the artefacts seem to originate from the Late Iron Age, and several assemblages point to cremation burials as evidenced by burnt and broken artefacts. Most of the burial sites are located in Jõgeva County (nos 42, 47, 49, 50). Also, most of the settlements (e.g. nos

41, 44, 47, 51) and the only Viking Age hoard from the southern parts of Estonia are also located in Jõgeva County. The Lahavere hoard from the late 11th century (no. 41) is relatively small in size, comprising 149 coins, but includes both rarities and more widespread types. The most remarkable coin in this hoard is an anonymous denier from Minden, Germany, which is only the second known example in the world and is exceptionally well-preserved (see more in Leimus, this volume).

There is no information on medieval or Modern Period cemeteries in the southern parts of Estonia, but half of the settlements have corresponding finds (e.g nos 41, 51, 140, 154). Similarly, medieval and Modern Period stray finds are also common (e.g. nos 46, 141, 146, 160). A more unique artefact, a bone pipe, was found without the use of a metal detector in the sand on the shore of Lake Peipsi (no. 146). The flute was radiocarbon dated to the 15th–16th centuries (Roio 2023). The Nina specimen is made of sheep's or goat's tibia bone, has four finger holes, a round-oval mouthpiece and no decoration (Fig. 5). Approximately twenty archaeological bone pipes are known from Estonia and they are mostly from the medieval period, fitting into a wider tradition of using bone pipes in Europe (Oras 2015). Two Early Modern Period hoards were found from Maramaa village, both of which were probably concealed in the early 17th century. One hoard (no. 144) was placed on the riverbank in two ceramic vessels, while the other (no. 145) was hidden in a crevice in a large stone (see more in Kiudsoo 2023). A curious collection of scrap iron was discovered in Selli (no. 48). The first finds were unearthed in 2021 and the rest were carefully excavated and documented in 2022. The assemblage includes a variety of artefacts from the medieval and Modern Period, but most of the finds cannot be dated more precisely. The finds include horseshoes, nails, buckles and various other fragments. Most of the items were broken, which helps to confirm their nature as scrap metal. It is likely that the finds were stored in a wooden box (Jegorov 2023). Lastly, a signet ring from Vesneri (no. 148; Fig 6.) should be mentioned. The ring is made of gold, with an onyx stone and decorated with enamel. The motifs used on the crest are common, such as a vase with three flowers, and the composition is rather modest (Russow 2022b). By studying the ring more closely, researchers were able to link the find to the Fritzberg family, originally coming from southern Sweden. The signet ring belonged to Johan Fritzberg, who used it in the last decades of the 17th century, and the last confirmed use of the very same ring (it has a distinctive deformation next to the initial) was in 1697 (Russow & Jaago 2023).

Fig. 5. A bone pipe from Lake Peipsi.

Jn 5. Luust vilepill Peipsi järvest.

Photo / Foto: Maili Roio

Fig. 6. A signet ring from Vesneri.

Jn 6. Vesneri sõrmus.

(TÜ 3061.)

Photo / Foto: Jaana Ratass

TURBULENT TIMES AT THE NATIONAL HERITAGE BOARD AND SCARCITY OF FINDS IN 2022

The year 2022 began with major structural changes within the MA. These changes affected the whole institution, including the Archaeology Department. With dwindling human resources and a minimal budget, solutions had to be found to organise the processing of public finds and their conservation. The MA decided to concentrate only on cases requiring urgent attention, while other cases were postponed. It became also difficult to outsource the archaeological reports (expert opinions), which has increased the delay in processing public finds in Estonia. As a solution, in-house workshops were held, where both professional archaeologists and archaeology students helped to identify the archaeological artefacts and their possible contexts. However, the workshops yielded only a modest number of reports when compared to the amount of artefacts. Moreover, the resources were stretched in a situation where a record number of public finds was handed over to the MA in 2021 (Kurisoo *et al.* 2022), many of which are still awaiting expert opinions. It is possible that these circumstances have also had some impact on the willingness of metal detectorists to communicate with heritage authorities and share their findings.

The decrease in the volume of public finds deserves pointing out. As the number of permit holders increases each year, the decline in the number of artefacts handed over to the MA is an alarming development. In 2022, artefacts were only handed in by less than ten percent of the licence holders, suggesting that the archaeological finds are severely underreported. The problem of illegal searches is certainly serious and the MA should do more to address the causes and consequences of this problem. In addition to issues of mutual trust and effective communication, changes in the regions of interest of more productive hobbyists or reduced search activity compared to the past also have some impact. For example, several new monuments in Pärnu County were discovered by a few hobby searchers, meaning that until 2022 Pärnu County was either underreported or outside of the main search areas in Estonia. Lastly, it should be noted that certain types of artefacts (e.g. some pieces of jewellery, certain types of coins etc.) are not actively collected by the state. There is still a reporting requirement in the search reports, but the finders can keep the artefacts if they wish and the MA has given them permission.

However, not all developments are worrying and have a negative undertone. The shorter form for the reports has made it less time consuming for archaeologists to complete expert opinions. The mandatory tabular appendix makes the information on artefacts machine-readable and more usable for research and heritage protection. The current system relies heavily on outsourcing experts and we hope that museums are ready to contribute to the production of expert opinions and to the conservation of archaeological finds. It is therefore to be hoped that processing public finds will continue at a faster pace than in 2022.

SUMMARISING REMARKS

The use of search devices has remained similar, with new licence holders entering the field. The geographical distribution of search areas continues to correlate with previously established patterns. Hobbyists are more active in the northern areas of Estonia and the most extensive data comes from Lääne-Viru and Järva Counties. There is less information on search activities from the western and southern parts of the country, with the exception of Pärnu County, where there has been an increase in discoveries. However, the number of reported finds has dropped almost across the country, with a notable decrease in the number of finds in Ida-Viru and Saare Counties. The underreporting of discoveries is concerning, especially

considering the growing number of individuals taking up metal detecting, but it needs further investigation. It is likely that slow processing of finds and long response / feedback time may be a contributing factor. 2022 was a challenging year for the MA, full of structural changes and budget cuts, resulting in delays in conservation and examination of artefacts.

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Table 1. Finds discovered by users of searching devices and stray finds reported to the National Heritage Board in 2022. Former parish name (if different from the present municipality name) is given in brackets.

Tabel 1. Otsinguvahendiga leitud ja juhuslikult avastatud leiud, mis jõudsid 2022. a Muinsuskaitseametisse. Sulgudes on esitatud kihelkond, juhul kui see erineb kehtivast haldusjaotusest.

Compiled by / Koostanud: Mari-Liis Posti, Nele Kangert, Sander Jegorov ja Tuuli Kurisoo

C – cemetery, burial place / kalmistu, matmispaik

F – stray find / juhuleid

H – hoard, deposit find / peitleid

S – settlement site / asulakoht

M – manufacturing site / tootmisega seotud muistis

No. / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no. / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
HARJUMAA								
1	Alansi	F	Kose	Brooch pin, mount, fragment of bracelet	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
2	Altküla, Harju-Risti	C/S	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Mount, fragment of penannular brooch and eye fibula	Roman Iron Age – Final Iron Age		R. Tammejuur	
3	Järveküla	F	Rae (Jüri)	Fragment of chain holder	Final Iron Age	AI 8766	Anonymous	
4	Keila town	F	Keila	Penannular brooch	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
5	Kibuna	F	Saue (Nissi)	Rectangular ornament link, fragment of cruciform pendant	Final Iron Age		A. Ilves	
6	Kloogarranna	F	Lääne-Harju (Keila)	Crossbow bolt, iron fragment	Middle Ages		E. Viira	
7	Kurna	F	Rae (Jüri)	Penannular brooch	Late Iron Age	AI 8779	Anonymous	
8	Meremõisa	M	Lääne-Harju (Keila)	Tools of smithy, slag	Modern Period		E. Viira	S. Jegorov
9	Mustu	S	Saue (Nissi)	Dress pin head, penannular brooch, cruciform pendant, bell, mounts, book clasps, buttons, buckle fragment, finger-ring	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		V. Tkachuk	
10	Mustu	S	Saue (Nissi)	Coin, mount	Late Viking Age, Middle Ages		V. Tkachuk	I. Leimus, N. Kangert

No. / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no./ Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
11	Nõmmeri	C	Kose	Fragments of bracelets and penannular brooches, mount, burnt fragments of copper alloy items	Viking Age – Final Iron Age		A. Agurauja	
12	Nõmmeri	C	Kose	Bracelet fragment	Viking Age – Final Iron Age		A. Agurauja	
13	Partsaare	C, F	Anija (Harju-Jaani)	Scale weight, bear-tooth pendant, pendant, mount, finger-ring, bracelet, fragment of copper alloy item	Final Iron Age, Modern Period		J. Gaidai	
14	Peetri	F	Rae (Jüri)	Bracelet	Late Iron Age	AI 8744	Anonymous	
15	Pohla	C?	Saue (Hageri)	Fragment of brooch pin, pendant, buckle, round brooch, iron item	Middle Ages – Modern Period		V. Tkachuk	
16	Raveliku	F	Kose	Fragment of penannular brooch, finger-rings, pendant	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		A. Agurauja	
17	Raveliku	F	Kose	Fragment of bracelet and copper alloy item	Late Iron Age?		A. Agurauja	
18	Salu	C, S	Rae (Harju-Jaani)	Scale weight, comb-shaped pendant, brooch pin, copper alloy item, detail of waist ornament	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		M. Kobets	
19	Saue	C	Saku (Keila)	Scabbard chape	11th – 12th c		U. Arm	
20	Saula	F	Kose	Silver penannular brooch fragment	12th – 14th c		J. Gaidai	
21	Saunja	S	Kuusalu (Jõelähtme)	Dress pin, pewter pendant, pewter mount	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		A. Ksentsov	
22	Tuulevälja	F	Rae (Jüri)	Bronze socketed axe	Late Bronze Age	AI 8679	D. Dmitrijev	K. Paavel
23	Vahetüki	F	Kose	Silver coin fragment	925–936?		A. Agurauja	
24	Vaidasoo	F	Rae (Jüri)	Penannular brooch	Late Iron Age		A. Sudovykh	
25	Vilivalla	F	Lääne-Harju (Risti)	Ear-scoop	Final Iron Age		R. Tammejuur	
26	Viskla	F, S	Kose	Coins, pendant, dress pin fragment, worked flint	Stone Age, Late Iron Age – Middle Ages		A. Agurauja	
HIIMUMAA								
27	Kassari	F	Hiiumaa (Pühalepa)	Bronze socketed axe	1300–900 BC		E. Järvekülg	K. Paavel
28	Reigi	F	Hiiumaa (Reigi)	Rectangular ornament link, mount, belt fitting	Final Iron Age, Modern Period		T. Eestalu	
IDA-VIRUMAA								
29	Aa	F	Lüganuse	Penannular brooch, finger-ring	Final Iron Age, Modern Period		E. Kessler	
30	Aa	H	Lüganuse	Dress pins, fragments of bracelet	Viking Age		Anonymous	
31	Alajõe	F	Alutaguse (Iisaku)	Penannular brooch, fragment of sheet pendant	Final Iron Age		G. Niinepuu	
32	Kahula	C?, S	Jõhvi	Zoomorphic pendant, fastening plates, rectangular ornament link	Final Iron Age		G. Niinepuu	
33	Lake Peipsi, Kauksi	F	Alutaguse (Iisaku)	Pendant	Middle Ages		G. Niinepuu	

No. / Nr	Site / Muistis	Type / Tüüp	Municipality / Vald	Finds / Leiud	Dating / Dateering	Inventory no. / Leiu nr	Discoverers / Avastajad	Expert / Ekspert
34	Remniku	F	Alutaguse (Iisaku)	Spearhead	Final Iron Age		G. Niinepuu	
35	Saka	H	Toila (Lüganuse)	Sheet pendants, fragments of tin vessel, finger-rings, belt fitting, pewter mount, coin pendants, fragments of copper alloy items	16th–17th c	AI 8738	Anonymous	E. Russow
36	Sompa	C	Jõhvi	Chain separator, mount	Final Iron Age		G. Niinepuu	
37	Uusküla	F	Alutaguse (Iisaku)	Fire-steel, nail	Middle Ages – Modern Period		G. Niinepuu	
38	Vodova	F	Narva-Jõesuu town (Vaivara)	Spearhead	Middle Ages		J. Tsumakov	
JÕGEVAMAA								
39	Alavere	S	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Finger-rings, dirham fragments	Late Iron Age		Anonymous	
40	Kassinurme	S	Jõgeva (Palamuse)	Fragments dirhams, coins, coin pendants, penannular brooch, finger-rings, tobacco pipe cleaner, knife handle detail, mount	Viking Age – Modern Period		R. Joost	
41	Lahavere	H, S	Põltsamaa	Silver coins, zoomorphic scale weight, sewing needle, fragment of silver item, brooch pin, flint	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	I. Leimus
42	Laiusevälja	C	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Mounts, ornament link, bracelets, chain fragments, spiral tubes, fragments of copper alloy items	Final Iron Age		E. Pärtelpoeg	
43	Liikatku	F	Jõgeva (Torma)	Penannular brooch	Final Iron Age		T. Sei	
44	Mustvee	S	Mustvee (Torma)	Flint spearhead	Late Neolithic / Early Bronze Age		M. Kilter	M. Roio
45	Painküla	F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Fastening plate with buckle, bell	Final Iron Age		R. Joost	
46	Pedja	F	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Signet ring	Modern Period		P. Laidre	
47	Pedja	C, S	Jõgeva (Laiuse)	Pendants, bracelet, rectangular ornament links, bead, belt separator, sheet pendant, burnt fragments of copper alloy items, fragment of tripod, coin pendant, pewter fragment	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		I. Kiudorf, P. Laidre	R.-M. Moon
48	Selli	M	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Horseshoe fragments, buckle, knife, nails, iron items, bone fragment	Middle Ages – Modern Period		I. Kiudorf, P. Laidre	S. Jegorov
49	Selli	C	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Cross-bar fibula, bell, rivet, bead, buckle, finger-rings, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. dress pin, burnt items)	Roman Iron Age – Final Iron Age		I. Kiudorf, P. Laidre	
50	Selli	C	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Bracelet fragment, burnt fragment	Final Iron Age		I. Kiudorf	
51	Selli	S	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Buckles, pendant fragment, finger-ring, slag, pyrite	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		I. Kiudorf, P. Laidre	

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52	Selli	C	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Rectangular ornament link, pendant, mount, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g finger-ring, waist ornament)	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		I. Kiudorf, P. Laidre	
53	Vadi	F	Mustvee (Torma)	Palstave	Late Bronze Age		Anonymous	K. Paavel
54	Vägeva	F	Jõgeva (Simuna)	Bead, bell, mount	Final Iron Age		P. Laidre	R.-M. Moon

JÄRVAMAA

55	Jalalõpe	C, S	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Bell, pewter mount, pendants, penannular brooches, fire steel, spearhead fragment, knife, fragments of iron items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Vaalundi, M. Suve	G. Vedru
56	Jalgsema	C, S	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Bells, bead, finger-rings, needle, fragments of copper alloy items (pendants, chain holder?, dress pin), mount, coin, pewter pendant	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Vaalundi, M. Suve	G. Vedru
57	Jalgsema	C, S	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Rectangular ornament link, coins, fragments of metal items (e.g dress pin, finger-ring, ring brooches, burnt items)	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		M. Suve	S. Nuut
58	Kaalepi	F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Bell, bracelet fragment	Final Iron Age		E. Promm	
59	Kaaruka	S	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Rectangular ornament link, mount, buttons, coins, fragments of copper alloy items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		E. Promm	
60	Kagavere	S?	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Mount, bell	Final Iron Age		E. Promm	
61	Kagavere	S	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Bells, finger-rings, bracelets, coin, dress pin fragment	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Vaalundi	G. Vedru
62	Kuksema	S	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Copper alloy kettle	Modern Period		H. Vaalundi	
63	Köisi	C, S	Järva (Peetri)	Rectangular ornament links, mounts, scale weight, bells, buckles, belt fittings, finger-rings, clay pipe fragments, fastening plate, ornament links, pendants, belt separator, penannular brooches, pewter mounts, coin pendants, coins, scabbard chape, fragment of cross-guard, bracelet, beads, ice nail, dress pin fragment, book clasp, tripod fragment, pottery, jewellery fragments	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		R. Lallu, A. Piirsalu	

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64	Metsla	S	Järva (Koeru)	Bracelets, penannular brooches, brooch pins, dress pin, buckles, pendants, bells, finger-rings, pewter mounts, pottery, coins, axe, knives, ice nails, slag, bone	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Vaalundi, M. Suve	G. Vedru
65	Metsla	H	Järva (Koeru)	Silver beads, glass beads, sheet pendants, round pendants with Calvary motif, brooches, finger-rings, coin pendants, mounts, chain fragments, fragments of copper alloy kettle, knife, pottery	Early 17th c		Anonymous	E. Russow
66	Metsla	S	Järva (Koeru)	Bell, chain holder, pendant, bracelet, signet ring, orthodox cruciform pendant, pewter mount, coin, brooch, spur, axe	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		M. Suve	
67	Metstaguse	S	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Penannular brooch pin, coin	Middle Ages		H. Vaalundi	G. Vedru
68	Näsuvere	S	Türi	Finger-ring, round brooch, sewing needle, fragment of copper alloy item	Middle Ages – Modern Period		R. Mättas	
69	Oeti	S	Paide town (Järva-Madise)	Pewter mount, button, burnt fragments of copper alloy items	Modern Period		E. Promm	
70	Ramma	C, S	Järva (Koeru)	Penannular brooches, bracelets, rectangular ornament link, coins, pendants, cruciform pendant, coin pendants, bells, finger-rings, knives, pottery, pewter mounts, spur detail, fragments of copper alloy jewellery, burnt fragments	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Vaalundi	G. Vedru
71	Seliküla	C, S	Järva (Järva-Jaani)	Bells, penannular brooches, fragments of copper alloy jewellery (e.g dress pins, finger-rings, bracelets), pendants, cruciform pendants, book clasp, cloth seal, coins, iron item, burnt fragment	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		M. Suve, H. Vaalundi	S. Nuut, G. Vedru
72	Valasti	C, S	Paide town (Järva-Jaani)	Bell, mounts, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g dress pin), coin pendants, coins, belt fitting	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		E. Promm	
73	Vetepere	F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Penannular brooch	Final Iron Age		E. Kessel	
74	Vetepere	F	Järva (Järva-Madise)	Sheet pendant fragments	Final Iron Age		E. Kessel	

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LÄÄNEMAA								
75	Liivi	C	Lääne-Nigula (Kullamaa)	Cross-guard fragment, scale weight, dress pin fragments, penannular brooch fragment, burnt items	Final Iron Age		J. Ojabstein	
76	Põgari-Sassi	S	Haapsalu (Ridala)	Buckle, pewter pendant	Modern Period		K. Vikat	
77	Üdruma	S	Lääne-Nigula (Kullamaa)	Chain holder, fragment of copper alloy item	Final Iron Age		J. Ojabstein	
LÄÄNE-VIRUMAA								
78	Iila	C?	Viru-Nigula	Bracelets fragments	Late Iron Age		Anonymous	
79	Iila	S	Viru-Nigula	Pennanular brooch, finger-ring with volute, pendant of St Anthony cross, signet ring	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Timm	
80	Iila	C?	Viru-Nigula	Pendant, pendant fragments, dress pin head, buckle, bracelets fragments, finger-rings, detail of knife sheath, fastening plate, sheet pendant, pewter bead	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
81	Iila	C, S	Viru-Nigula	Rectangular ornament links, arrowhead, brooch pin, mounts, bracelets fragments, fastening plate, dress pin head, bead, finger-rings, bells, knife handle details, burnt fragments of copper alloy items, belt fittings, knife, fish-spear, iron items	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages		A. Timm, Anonymous	
82	Iila	S	Viru-Nigula	Coin pendant	Modern Period		A. Timm	
83	Jõepere	S	Kadrina	Cloth seal, pin fragment, sheet pendant fragment?, fragments of copper alloy items	Modern Period		Anonymous	
84	Lauli	F	Haljala	Cruciform pendant	Middle Ages	AI 8747	Anonymous	
85	Liivaküla	F	Väike-Maarja	Penannular brooch pin blank	Final Iron Age		L. Roots	
86	Mõdriku	C, S	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Equal-armed brooch fragments, pendant, coin pendant, bell, ring, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. bracelet, dress pins, buckle, mount, loop for cauldron handle), burnt fragments	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		T. Vaide	

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87	Mõdriku	C, S	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Penannular brooches, scale weight, rectangular ornament link, bells, beads, fastening plates, finger-rings, detail of knife sheath, pendants, sheet pendant, coins, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. crossbow-shaped fibula, dress pin, buckles, loop for cauldron handle, brace- lets), spur, book clasps, belt fitting, mounts, pewter mounts, burnt fragments	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		T. Vaide	
88	Mõdriku	F	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Button	Modern Period		T. Vaide	
89	Mõdriku	S	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Rectangular ornament link, penannular brooch, coin fragment	Late Iron Age		T. Vaide	
90	Mõdriku	S	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Fragments items (e.g bracelets, sheet pendant, pendant, penannular brooch, buckles), coin, pottery, belt fitting	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		T. Vaide	
91	Männikvälja	F	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Heart shaped brooch, leath- er belt with belt fittings	Modern Period		T. Vaide	
92	Nugeri	S	Viru-Nigula	Dirham, dress pin with disk shaped head, penannular brooch, pewter pendant	Late Iron Age – Middle Ages		A. Timm, Anonymous	
93	Nugeri	F	Viru-Nigula	Bracelet, book clasp	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
94	Nõmme	S	Väike-Maarja	Cruciform pendants, buck- les, brooch, copper alloy item fragment	Modern Period		L. Roots	
95	Pandivere	F	Väike-Maarja	Pendant	Middle Ages		L. Roots	
96	Patika	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Bell	Final Iron Age		J. Gaidai	
97	Pruuna	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Bells, bracelet fragment	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
98	Rägavere	F	Tapa (Ambla)	Dress pin fragments, chain fragment, pendant, finger-ring, penannular brooch	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
99	Rägavere	S	Tapa (Ambla)	Mount	Final Iron Age		J. Gaidai	
100	Tirbiku	S	Kadrina	Coin pendant, bell, cloth seal, finger-ring, belt fitting, brooch pin, chain fragment, metal item	Modern Period		Anonymous	

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101	Vetiku	C, S	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Penannular brooches, dirham, chain holder, dress pin heads, bells, mounts, rectangular ornament links, buckles, scale weight, finger-rings, pendants, jewellery fragments (e.g. crossbow-shaped fibula, mount with faces, bracelets, neck ring), thimble, loop for cauldron handle, belt fittings, coin pendants, decorative item, book clasp, burnt fragments	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		T. Vaide	
102	Vetiku	F	Vinni (Viru-Jaagupi)	Burnt fragment of copper alloy item	Final Iron Age		T. Vaide	
103	Villakvere	F	Väike-Maarja (Laiuse)	Pommel	Middle Ages		P. Laidre	R.-M. Moon
104	Äntu	F	Väike-Maarja	Signet ring	Modern Period		L. Roots	
105	Ärina	S	Väike-Maarja	Penannular brooch, pendant, scale weight, silver coin, bracelet fragments, pewter mount	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		L. Roots	

PÕLVAMAA

106	Hurmi	F	Kanepi	Roman coin	2nd c		K. Soo	
107	Valgjärve	C	Kanepi	Bracelets, bones	Final Iron Age		T. Tammetalu	

PÄRNUMAA

108	Eametsa	F	Tori (Pärnu)	Seal matrix	15th c		M. Puuram	E. Russow
109	Eametsa	S	Tori (Pärnu)	Zoomorphic pendant fragment	Final Iron Age		M. Puuram	
110	Häädemeeste	F	Häädemeeste	Spearhead	Late Iron Age		A. Roosmaa	E. Heinloo
111	Lehu	C, S	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Scale weight, finger-rings, dirham, pendant, bone/ antler gaming piece	Late Iron Age		M. Puuram	
112	Lehu	C	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Dress pin head, fragment of copper alloy jewellery	Late Iron Age		M. Puuram, H. Ööpik	
113	Lehu	C, S	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Silver coins, bells, finger-ring, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. pendant, bracelet, pin, spoon), bone fragment	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Ööpik	
114	Lehu	S	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Spur, pendant fragment, coin fragment	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		H. Ööpik	
115	Lindi	S	Pärnu town (Audru)	Coins	16th c		M. Puuram	
116	Metsaküla	H	Häädemeeste (Pärnu)	Bracteates, horseshoe, nails	Middle Ages		Anonymous	
117	Metsaküla	H	Häädemeeste (Pärnu)	Tin bottle, coin pendant, brooches, finger-ring	Early 18th c		Anonymous	E. Russow
118	Metsaküla	S	Häädemeeste (Pärnu)	Knives, finger-ring, pottery, key, daub fragments, charcoal	Modern Period		Anonymous	

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119	Metsaküla	F	Häädemeeste (Pärnu)	Spearhead	Final Iron Age?		Anonymous	
120	Metsaküla	S	Häädemeeste	Socketed axes, horseshoe, nails	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
121	Metsavere	F	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Spoon fragment	Modern Period		M. Puuram	
122	Pööravere	S	Põhja-Pärnumaa (Pärnu-Jaagupi)	Pendants, penannular brooch, silver coins	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		M. Puuram	
123	Tahkuranna	F	Häädemeeste	Coins	Modern Period		M. Puuram	
124	Võitra	F	Lääneranna (Mihkli)	Scale weight, pommel, dress pin, spoon or knife handle, silver coin, rectangular ornament links, mounts, bells, pendant, penannular brooch fragments, metal item	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		R. Treumann	
125	Võitra	C	Lääneranna (Mihkli)	Dress pin head, ring, scale weight, sheet pendant, rectangular ornament link	Final Iron Age		R. Treumann	
126	Võitra	H?	Lääneranna (Mihkli)	Roman denarii	2nd c		Anonymous	
RAPLAMAA								
127	Atla	C, F	Rapla (Juuru)	Penannular brooches, brooch pins, mounts, rectangular ornament link, pendant, fastening plate, scale weight, fragments of jewellery (e.g. neck rings, bell, bracelets, buckle, chains, details of waist ornament), burnt fragments, knife fragment	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		K. Kõiv	
128	Hõreda	C	Rapla (Juuru)	Pendants, bracelets, spiral tubes, rectangular ornament link, mounts, penannular brooches, brooch pin, pewter mount, silver coin fragment, burnt fragments of copper alloy items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		K. Kõiv	
129	Lümandu	C	Märjamaa	Buckles, bells, brooch pin, mounts, silver coin fragments, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. penannular brooches, bracelets, burnt fragments), axe fragment, book clasp, metal items	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Skrõpnik	
130	Lümandu	C	Märjamaa	Comb pendant, brooch pins, mounts, fastening plate, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. penannular brooches, buckles, chains), knife fragment, book clasp	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		L. Vassiljev	
131	Pae	F	Kehtna (Juuru)	Penannular brooch, bell, knife handle	Final Iron Age – Early Modern Period		H. Ööpik	

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SAAREMAA								
132	Lassi	F	Saaremaa (Anseküla)	finger-rings, fastening plate, knife handle detail?, fragment of iron item	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Raun	
133	Länga	F	Saaremaa (Anseküla)	Belt with rings and rectangular ornament links	Final Iron Age	SM 10954	Anonymous	
134	Lümanda	F	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Dress pin fragment, silver coin, coin pendant	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		K. Laane	
135	Püha	F	Saaremaa (Püha)	Mount	Modern Period		R. Jasmin	R. Keire
136	Rahuste	F	Saaremaa (Jämaja)	Penannular brooch	Final Iron Age		K. Laane	
137	Reo	C, S	Saaremaa (Püha)	Rectangular ornament links, mounts, pewter pendant, pewter mounts, scale weight, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. finger-ring), iron item with ring and cross, silver coins, padlock, cloth seal, pipe fragment, metal items	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Rand, K. Kask	
138	Tammese	S	Saaremaa (Kihelkonna)	Silver coins, fragments of copper alloy items (brooch pin, finger-ring, kettle, burnt item), iron item	Late Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
139	Veeriku	C, S	Saaremaa (Valjala)	Mounts, buckles, bridle bit, pendants, spiral tube, push-key spring locks, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. penannular brooch, dress pins), finger-rings, ring brooches, book clasps	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		Anonymous	
TARTUMAA								
140	Aakre	S	Elva (Rõngu)	Pendants, mount, coin pendants, finger-ring, coins, fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. sheet pendant, brooch, finger-ring)	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		A. Lehtsaar	
141	Alasoo	F	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Mount	Late Middle Ages		P. Kiuru	E. Russow
142	Kavastu	F, S	Luunja (Tartu-Maarja)	Adze	Neolithic		L. Helstein	
143	Kurista	F	Kastre (Võnnu)	Spearhead	Final Iron Age		Anonymous	
144	Maramaa	H	Tartu (Tartu-Maarja)	Pottery, silver wire kopecks	17th c		Anonymous	M. Kiudsoo
145	Maramaa	H	Tartu (Tartu-Maarja)	Silver coins	17th c		Anonymous	M. Kiudsoo
146	Lake Peipsi	F	Peipsiääre (Kodavere)	Bone flute	Early Modern Period		G. Katasonov	M. Roio
147	Sassi	F	Nõo (Rõngu)	Cross-bar fibula, detail of knife sheath	Roman Iron Age – Late Iron Age?		M. Mettis	
148	Vesneri	F	Tartu (Tartu-Maarja)	Golden signet ring	End of 17th c	TÜ 3061	M. Visnapuu	E. Russow

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VALGAMAA								
149	Koikküla	C	Valga (Hargla)	Bracelets fragments	Late Iron Age		A. Hanimägi	P. Kama
150	Tiidu	F	Otepää (Sangaste)	Head-shield fibula, cloth seal	Roman Iron Age, Modern Period		M. Mettis	
VILJANDIMAA								
151	Kookla	S	Viljandi (Suure-Jaani)	Signet rings	Modern Period		A. Kägu	
152	Kookla	F	Viljandi (Suure-Jaani)	Scale weights, rectangular ornament link	Final Iron Age		A. Kägu	
153	Kurnuvere	F	Põhja-Sakala (Suure-Jaani)	Fragments of copper alloy items (e.g. loop for cauldron handle)	Final Iron Age – Middle Ages		P. Kanep	
154	Lalsi	S	Viljandi (Kolga-Jaani)	Mount, padlock, whetstone	Middle Ages – Early Modern Period		U. Kuusik	R. Keire
155	Mustapali	C, S	Viljandi (Paistu)	Penannular brooches, brooch pins, pendant, mounts, chain separator, chain fragment, knife handle details, coins	Final Iron Age – Modern Period		T. Grossthal	
156	Supsi	F	Põhja-Sakala (Kõpu)	Chain holder	Final Iron Age		H. Raidma	
157	Sürgavere	F	Põhja-Sakala (Suure-Jaani)	Rectangular ornament link, ornament link	Final Iron Age		A. Kägu	
VÕRUMAA								
158	Hilläkeste	S	Setomaa	Roman copper coin, pewter pendant, fire-steel	Roman Iron Age, Final Iron Age		M. Irdla	
159	Lindsi	F	Setomaa	Signet ring	Modern Period		M. Irdla	
160	Oe	F	Antsla (Urvaste)	Coin pendant	Middle Ages		J. Kiidron	I. Leimus, K. Karro

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2022. AASTA DETEKTORI- JA JUHULEIUD NING MURED LEIDUDEST TEATAMISE JA MENETLEMISEGA

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Artikkel annab esmalt ülevaate 2022. aasta jooksul Muinsuskaitseametisse (MA) jõudnud detektori- ja juhuleidudest. Lisaks käsitletakse nende esemetega seotud probleeme (nt leidudest vähene teatamine) ja väljakutseid MA vaates (nt struktuurireform). Otsinguvahendi kasutamine pakub avalikkusele jätkuvalt huvi ja 2022. aasta lõpuks oli Eestis juba ligi tuhat loaomanikku. Samas on murettekitaavaks arenguks leiateadete arvu langus, mis torkab eriti silma võrreldes 2021. aastaga. Arheoloogiliste leidude ja leiukohtade info põhineb tabelis 1 esitatud informatsioonil, kuid suur osa nendest määrangutest on esialgsed ja võivad ajas muutuda.

Võrreldes varasemate aastatega on märkimisväärselt vähem teada antud põhjapoolsest Eestist kogu-

tud leidudest, mis on eriti tajutat Harjumaa (26 leiukohta) ja Ida-Virumaa (10 leiukohta) näitel (tabel 1, jn 1). Lääne-Virumaa (28 leiukohta), Järvamaa (20 leiukohta) ja Raplamaa (5 leiukohta) teadete hulk on võrreldav eelmiste aastatega. Leiukontekstidest domineerivad asulakohad ja matusepaigad. Põhjapoolsema Eesti vanimad leiud on kaks kiviaegset töödeldud tulekivi tüki (nr 26), pronksiaega dateeritav putkkirves (nr 22) ja rooma rauaaegne silmiksõlg (nr 2). Kõige enam saadi leide muinasaja lõpusajanditest ning võib arvata, et mitmed vastava dateeringuga leiud on seotud põletusmatustega kalmetega (nt 2, 11, 56, 63, 71, 81, 87, 101, 129, 130) või asulakohtadega (nt nr 2, 9, 61, 64, 89, 92). Viikingiajast on pärit Aa peitleid (nr 30), mis saadi märgalalt ning mis koosneb kahest ristpeaga

ehtenõelast ja spiraalkäevõru katkenditest. Kolm haruldasemat eset pärineb hilisrauaajast, neist üks on antropomorfse motiiviga mõõgatupe otsik Sauelt (nr 19; jn 2: 1). Sellise motiiviga leidu ei ole varasemalt lähiregionist teada, kuid oma kuju ja tüübi poolest võiks olla tegu 11.–12. sajandi esemega. Teise erilise esemena saab esile tõsta Vilivalla kõrvalusikat (nr 25; jn 2: 2), mis Soome paralleelide põhjal võiks samuti pärineda 11.–12. sajandist. Kolmas põnev avastus on Ärina ripats (nr 105), mis kujutab ratsanikku hobuse seljas (jn 2: 3). Leid on kolmas ratsanikke kujutav ripats Eestist, kuid neist kõige kehvema teostusega.

Kesk- ja uusaegsed leiud on samuti arvukad, neist enamik on rõivaste ja ehetega seotud leiud, esindatud on ka igapäevased väikesemad tarbeesemed. Leiukontekstidest erilisem on Meremõisa sepikoda (nr 8), kust leiti sepatööriistu ja šlakki. Avastati ka kaks varauusaegset aaret, millest tagasihoidlikuma koostisega leid saadi Ida-Virumaalt Sakast (nr 35). Saka aare koosneb kahest tinakannust ja kümnest halvast hõbedast tehtud rinnalehest. Järvamaalt leitud Metsla-Ellavere aarde (nr 65) moodustavad arvukad hõbeehted (nt krõllid, ripatsid, sõrmused), klaas-helmed ning ripatsmündid, mis olid metallist anuma sisse peidetud tõenäoliselt 17. sajandi alguses.

Varasemate aastatega sarnaselt on läänepoolsest Eestist vähem informatsiooni hobiotsijate leidude kohta kui teistest piirkondadest (jn 1, tabel 1). Erandiks on aga Pärnu maakond (19 leiukohta), mis on kogu andmestiku ainuke maakond, mille kohta on rohkem infot kui varasemalt. Selle arengu taga on eelkõige paar aktiivset hobiotsijat, kes on seda piirkonda lähemalt uurima hakanud. Leidudest anti teada ka Hiiumaalt (2 leiukohta) ja Läänemaalt (3 leiukohta). Murettekitavaks on kujunenud olukord Saaremaal (8 leiukohta), kus leidudest teatamine on tugevalt langenud, kuigi tegu on detektoristide seas populaarse piirkonnaga. Leiukontekstide jaotumine on sarnane põhjapoolsemale Eestile, kus on informatsiooni eelkõige asulakohtade ja matusepaikade kohta. Leiti ka kolm aaret, millest Võitra aarde (nr 126) koostisesse kuuluvad hõbedast valmistatud Rooma denaarid, mis on Eestis seniajani haruldased. Metsakülalt saadi kaks aaret, millest esimene (nr 116) sisaldas keskaegseid brakteate. Teine Metsaküla peitleid (nr 117) on aga veidi erilisem 18. sajandi algupoolel maapõue jäänud kogum, mis oli peidetud tinapudelisse (nn kruvipudel; jn 4). Sinna kuulusid veel süda-, vits-, ja kättega sõlg, kihlasõrmust, Karl XI kahemargane (1665) ja kogum vahatükke.

Läänepoolse Eesti vanim leid on Kassarist avastatud putkkirves (nr 27), millele ajaliselt järgnevad mainitud Võitra denaarid (nr 126) ning ülejäänud materjal on juba hilisem, ulatudes nooremast

rauaajast uusajani. Kõige erilisem leid on Saaremaal Längast (nr 133) leitud vööketi (jn 3), mille teeb tähelepanuväärseks mitu asjaolu. Vööketid on küll iseloomulikud naiste (ja laste) ehted, kuid kõik varem avastatud vööketid on leitud katkenditena. Länga leid on säilinud aga täies pikkuses (2,5 m) ning seda kaunistavad kuljused ning ristripats. Vööketide dateering on tavaliselt 12.–13. sajand, kuid Länga leiu juures olev ripats ja kuljused osutavad mõnevõrra hilisemale kasutusele. Leiu juures tuleb mainida ka selle keerulist leidmisloogu, mis iseloomustab hobiotsimisega seotud probleeme Eestis ka üldisemalt. Nimelt ei olnud leidjal otsinguvahendi luba ja ta leidis vööketi teadlikult seadust rikkudes. Mõne aja möödudes otsustas ta leiu uuesti maha matta ja andis sellest ka MA-le teada, kes leiu ja leiupeiga dokumenteerisid.

Üleantud leidude hulk vähenes märgatavalt ka lõunapoolses Eestis, kuigi langus maakonniti on väiksem kui põhja- ja läänepoolses Eestis (jn 1, tabel 1). Varasemate aastatega kõrvaltades on leidudest teatamine jäänud võreldavaks Jõgevamaal (16 leiukohta), Põlvamaal (2 leiukohta), Valgamaal (1 leiukoht), Viljandimaal (7 leiukohta) ning Võrumaal (3 leiukohta). Tartu maakonnast on viimaste aastate jooksul üha vähem teateid ning sel aastal jõudis tabelisse vaid 10 leiukohta. Lisaks arvukatele juhuleidudele on informatsiooni asulakohtade (nt nr 40, 51, 140, 158), matusepaikade (nt nr 49, 107, 149, 155), aarete (nr 41, 144, 145) ja isegi ühe vanametallitagavara kohta (nr 48).

Lõunapoolse Eesti vanimad leiud on Kavastust leitud kiviaegne talb (nr 142), mis saadi Emajõest kalastamise käigus. Teinegi kiviaegne leid saadi ilma otsinguvahendit kasutamata ja tegu on haruldase tulekivist nooleotsaga Mustveest (nr 44), mis leiti juba 2009. aastal. Mainimist väärib ka pronksiaegne õlgkirves Vadist (nr 53) Jõgevamaalt. Õlgkirveid on Eestist teada alla 20 leiu ja enamik neist on seni avastatud Edela- ja Kesk-Eestist. Mitmelt poolt saadi ka rooma rauaaegseid leide, nt kärbissõlgi (nr 49, 147), peakilpsõlg (nr 150) ja Rooma münte (nr 106, 158). Kuigi muinasaja teisest poolest saadi arvukalt leide, siis erilisem neist on Lahavere aardest (nr 41) pärit Saksa münt Mindenist, mis on ülemaailmselt haruldane.

Suur osa kesk- ja uusaegseid leide on juhuleidud, mis esindavad levinud esemetüüpe. Esile tasub tõsta otsinguvahendita leitud luust vilepilli Peipsi kaldalt (nr 146). Vilepill on valmistatud lamba/kitse sääreluust, sellel on neli sõrmeava ja ornament puudub (jn 5). Leid on dateeritud radiosüsinikumeetodil, mis näitab selle kasutust 15.–16. sajandil. Varauusaega saab dateerida ka kaks mündiaaret Maramaalt, kusjuures esimene neist (nr 144) oli peidetud jõekaldale kahe nõu sisse ning teine (nr 145) suure kivi sees

olevasse lõhesse. Sellist (nr 48) saadi lisa 2021. aastal avastatud vanametalli tagavarale, mida 2022. aastal hoolikalt uuriti ja dokumenteeriti. Leiud esindavad enamasti katkiseid (raud)esemeid (naeltest ja hobuseraudadest pannaldeni), mida võidi hoiustada puidust kasti sees. Viimase leiuna tuleb ära märkida Vesnerist (nr 148, jn 6) leitud kullast pitsatsõrmust, mille kivi on oonüksist ja dekooris on kasutatud veel emaili. Pitsatiosa vapi motiivid on laialtlevinud (vaas kolme lillega), kuid erinevatele allikatele toetudes võib siduda selle Lõuna-Rootsist pärit Fritzbergide perekonnaga, täpsemalt oli sõrmuse omanik Johan Fritzberg, kes kasutas seda 17. sajandi lõpus.

Viimase teemana on artiklis välja toodud 2022. aasta alguses MA-s toimunud struktuurimuudatused, mis vajutasid pitseri kogu ameti tegevustele, sh arheoloogia osakonna võimekusele leidudega tegeleda. Vähenenud inimressursi ja minimaalse eelarve tingimustes tegeleti esmajärjekorras vaid erilisemate leidude konserveerimise ja nendest eksperdihinnangute koostamisega. Leiuekspertiise tehti ka talgute korras, kaasates arheolooge väljastpoolt MA-d ja arheoloogia eriala üliõpilasi. Siiski ei katnud sel-

line tegevus vajadust, sest 2021. aastal jõudis MA-sse rekordkogus leide, millest paljud ootavad veel tänaseni oma järke. Võimalik, et tagasiside pikk ootamine on üks põhjustest, miks 2022. aastal anti ametile üle senisest märgatavalt vähem leide ja leidudest teatas alla kümne protsendi loomanikest. Seega on tõenäoline, et paljud avastused ei jõua MA-ni ja sellele kitsaskohale tuleks eraldi tähelepanu pöörata. Samas on oluline märkida, et mõningane langus maakondade kaupa võib olla seletatav ka aktiivsete hobiotsijate uurimispiirkondade muutusega. Teine aspekt on seotud riigipoolse kogumispoliitikaga: üha rohkem leide jääb hobiotsijatele soovi korral kätte, aga nendestki leidudest tuleb esmalt riigile teada anda. Positiivse arenguna saab välja tuua, et lühemad eksperdihinnangud koos tabelikujul esitatava lisaga täidavad oma eesmärgi: hinnangud valmivad kiiremini ning informatsioon on masinloetav ja paremini kasutatav. Loodetavasti on ka muuseumid valmis arheoloogilisi leide konserveerima ja eksperdihinnangute tegemisse rohkem panustama, mis annab lootust, et leidude menetlemine võiks toimuda edaspidi kiiremini kui 2022. aastal.